

Integrating Trees on Farms

Three questions were presented to the panel following presentations by Hilary Grant and Jenny Kane. Some responses are given in section 1, below, from the perspective of silvopasture where trees are introduced into grazing areas or where sections of woodland are created adjacent to grazing areas. This is followed, in section 2, by a summary of research and research gaps relating to animal health and welfare in such systems which is pertinent to their adoption.

Section 1.

- How can the benefits of tree planting on farms be maximised for each of (i) climate adaptation, (ii) climate mitigation, and (iii) biodiversity enhancement?

Response: Maximum benefits in silvopasture can be achieved by the introduction of stands of appropriate tree species to provide shade and shelter during periods of extreme weather which are predicted to increase. These adaptations may be beneficial for productivity but also for water conservation during prolonged dry and hot weather. For example, dairy cattle maintained in silvopasture conditions during hot dry summer weather in Brazil had reduced physiological heat stress, increased grazing time, decreased standing time and decreased water intake compared to cattle raised in conventional pastures (Skonieski *et al.*, 2021). In a study in the USA, cattle raised in silvopasture conditions in pastures planted with a range of nut species and native deciduous and coniferous species had similar daily weight gain to those raised on conventional pasture (Amorim *et al.*, 2023). The authors estimated that the conventional pasture system would require approximately four times more land to yield equivalent net productivity as a result of the increased yields of nuts etc. in the silvopasture system (Amorim *et al.*, 2023). From a climate mitigation perspective, such efficiency/productivity increases are highly relevant. Closer to home, the shelter provided by stands of trees during and immediately after lambing could prevent neo-natal losses, for example, which represent a major loss to the Scottish livestock industry and contribute to inefficiencies relevant to carbon emissions. From an adaptation perspective, riparian planting has the potential to protect pastures from flooding and also to use undesirable grazing areas for woodland (for example, wet areas with high liver-fluke risk being planted with alder, willow or birch and fenced off to prevent livestock access). Biodiversity enhancement advantages are clear and obvious with the introduction of native tree species, less so with non-natives. Some unintended consequences of increased biodiversity should be considered (see Section 2, below).

- What are the key principles for determining what trees should be planted, where, and in what quantity to have an effect, for each of these three goals respectively?

Response: “Right tree in the right place” principles are being used, for example, by the Integrated Tree Network and will partly depend on the farmer’s objectives (shelter, shade, riparian, commercial crop). Given the range of grazing pasture types in Scotland, this will need to be highly flexible, with upland grazing likely to be challenging in terms of limitations in the tree species appropriate for such terrain. The impacts on each of the concepts (adaptation, mitigation and biodiversity) will only be fully maximized by farmer engagement via peer-to-peer learning and demonstration from respected peers. Interestingly, the farmers engaged in the Integrated Tree Network identified “biodiversity” as their key motivation for adopting silvopasture. Economic drivers through biodiversity audits and carbon audits/credits need to be co-designed to maximise impacts on adaptation, mitigation and biodiversity.

- What is the economic impact for farmers for each type of planting trees on farms?

Response: This will depend to a very large extent on the objective of the farmer for adoption. Economic incentives through payments for woodland assessments will mitigate early adoption costs but costs of upkeep of fencing, maintenance of the tree crop etc may be barriers to adoption in some systems. There may be increased costs to livestock farmers through losses of livestock to predation and disease and/or treatment costs of disease but these are largely unknown currently (see section 2, below)

Section 2. Summary of research and research gaps relating to animal health and welfare in such systems.

Improved livestock health and welfare in silvopasture systems have been considered in several publications, focusing on reduced heat stress encountered by animals grazing in shaded areas, for example (Amorim *et al.*, 2023; Skonieski *et al.*, 2021). There is a paucity of peer-reviewed published research on the impacts of such systems on unintended negative animal health consequences through increased predation and transmission of infectious disease.

i) Predation

There is a concern amongst some livestock keepers that introduction of trees into grazing land will result in an increase in local populations of predators including corvids, foxes and badgers occupying this niche. This represents a research gap for the study of impacts of predation on livestock production in systems where silvopasture has been introduced, particularly where woodlands have been created or where livestock have been allowed access to existing woodland for grazing.

ii) Infectious disease

A general principle of infectious disease transmission is that proximity to a pathogen source increases the likelihood of infection from that source, hence the increase in infectious disease transmission when animals are brought into close proximity (a lack of “social distancing”). An extreme example of this is in housed vs. outdoor-raised sheep where maedi-visna virus has transmission rates ~1000 times faster in housed sheep than in outdoor-raised (Illius *et al.*, 2020). Silvopasture systems may present the opportunity for animals to gather in larger numbers in smaller areas around trees than they would in open pasture, while seeking shade or shelter for example. This potentially represents an increased opportunity for transmission of infectious diseases caused by viruses, bacteria and fungi or parasites such as sheep scab mites (*Psoroptes ovis*). As well as increased risk of transmission from direct contact, sheep suffering from sheep scab rub themselves against stationary structures such as fence posts and trees to alleviate symptoms and this behaviour dislodges parasites which are then viable for up to 16 days to re-infest other hosts.

iii) Vector-borne disease

In a study performed on 16 livestock farms in Denmark, the presence of deciduous trees within 500 m of the farms resulted in higher numbers of *Culicoides obsoletus s.s.*, while presence of wetlands increased the numbers of *Culicoides punctatus* and *Culicoides pulicaris* (Nielsen *et al.*, 2014). *Culicoides* spp. midges, including *C. obsoletus*, are the principal vectors of some of the most devastating vector-borne diseases of livestock including bluetongue virus (Melhorn *et al.*, 2007) and Schmallenberg virus (Wernike and Beer, 2024). Ticks also represent major vectors of diseases of both humans and livestock. A recent study from Italy demonstrated that cattle grazing in silvopasture systems were parasitized by higher numbers of ticks than those in open pasture and that the ticks were

harbouring pathogenic *Rickettsia* spp belonging to the “spotted fever” group (Jimale *et al.*, 2024). The increase in biodiversity associated with integrating trees into livestock grazing areas has the potential to increase exposure to arthropod vectors including midges, ticks, biting flies and mosquitoes which exploit the canopy as a resting place.

iv) Gastrointestinal nematodes

The production-limiting effects of infection with gastrointestinal nematodes (GIN) result in one of the largest economic impacts on both sheep and cattle systems in the UK. In addition, the inefficiencies and physiological impacts associated with GIN infection contribute to increased greenhouse gas emission from the sector (Rose Vineer *et al.*, 2020). GIN with a direct lifecycle develop into their infective stages on pasture after hatching from eggs in livestock faeces. One of the key factors governing the survival of these infective larvae is exposure to ultraviolet (UV) radiation with higher levels of exposure resulting in substantial losses of infective larvae (van Dijk *et al.*, 2009). The protection from direct UV exposure afforded by trees in a silvopasture system, combined with increased animal density around trees in a silvopasture system has the potential to result in increased parasitism. In relation to this, cattle faeces containing GIN larvae which were maintained for 15 days in non-shaded conditions contained significantly lower numbers of viable GIN larvae compared to those maintained in shaded areas for the same period (Bilotto *et al.*, 2018). There is a general paucity of data around this issue for sheep and cattle, but horses grazed in a silvopasture system in North-West Spain had significantly increased infection with GIN when compared to those managed in open pasture farms (Francisco *et al.*, 2009).

Conclusion

Considerable research gaps exist in the literature surrounding the unintended consequences of the increased biodiversity associated with silvopasture systems in Scotland. Research into the potential risks, and their mitigation, represented by increased exposure of livestock to predators and pathogens as a result of adopting silvopasture in Scottish livestock farms would assist in increasing the levels of adoption of this practice in the sector. One of the key predictors for adoption has been identified as “Trust in the source of the information” (Zabala *et al.*, 2025) and considerable weight should be given to this in the delivery of the research.

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